

Characterization and Molecular Weight Determinations of Some Organo Poly(aminium phosphate)s—Part V†

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Paper chromatographic studies and conductance measurements have been used to characterize a few long chain poly(aminium phosphate)s of general composition $(BHPO_3)_n$ (where BH=organic cations). Number average molecular weights of these polymers have been determined by titrating pH-metrically the poly(phosphoric acids)s obtained by passing the aqueous solution of $(BHPO_3)_n$ derivatives through a column of cation exchange resin. Molecular weight determinations by viscometric data also confirm their long chain polymeric character. The viscosity average molecular weights have been calculated from improved values of intrinsic viscosity, which are determined according to the modified procedure suggested by Nagy, using the linear transformation $G=AF+B$ of usual extrapolation of η_{sp}/C vs C . Here $G=Y/\alpha-x$, $F=x/\alpha-x$ and $\alpha=x_m+x_M$ where $Y=\eta_{sp}/C$ and x_m and x_M denote minimum and maximum concentration.

THE chemistry of inorganic phosphate polymers has been extensively reviewed by several workers^{1,2} from time to time. However, systematic investigations in the field of poly(aminium-phosphate)s have not been tried. Only few ammonium³ and uronium polyphosphates^{4,5} of low molecular weights have been prepared and have been used as fertilizers successfully.

Guanidine, an analogue of urea, has been used for the purification of tetrakisphosphate by recrystallization⁶. Watters *et al*⁷ have studied the reaction of guanidine and tetrakisphosphate anion. Recently, some guanidinium oligophosphates⁸ of composition $(H_2CN_3)_nH_{n+2}P_nO_{3n+1}$ ($n=1-10$ have been) prepared and have been found to be useful flame retardants for paper and wood.

In the present paper, synthesis of some poly(aminium-phosphate)s of compositions, $(I_a - I_i)$ have been described. The long chain polymeric nature of these derivatives has been elucidated by paper chromatographic analysis⁹ and conductance studies¹⁰. The molecular weights have been determined by end group titration technique¹¹ and viscosity measurements¹².

where R :

Experimental

Reagents : All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Extra pure water was used for preparing the solutions. Recrystallized organic compounds were used for the preparation of poly(aminium phosphate)s.

Synthesis : A technique^{13,14} involving the following reaction :

Aqueous solutions of poly(lithium phosphate) and organic amine hydrochlorides were mixed in 1 : 1 mole ratio. Monomer formula weight of poly lithium metaphosphate was used. The pH of the resulting solution was adjusted below 4. The lowering of the pH was considered essential in view of the fact that at this pH the lithium ions are loosely associated with the phosphate chain anions. The addition of the organic amine or amide hydrochloride leads to the association of these cations with the phosphate chain anions. Precipitation from the clear solution was carried out by the addition of 2-propanol. The precipitate settled down after cooling for half an hour. It was washed repeatedly with 2-propanol to extract as much water out of it as possible. Lithium chloride, so formed, was also removed by repeated washing with 2-propanol. It was confirmed by the absence of lithium ion in the final product. Finally the product, i.e. the poly(aminium phosphate) was dried under vacuum at room temperature. The composition of these poly(aminium phosphate)s of general formula $(BHPO_3)_n$ was established by analysing them for nitrogen¹⁵ and phosphorus¹⁶. The results of analysis are recorded in Table 1.

† Part—IV P. C. VYAS, C. K. OZA, R. S. SHARMA and K. O. JAIN, *Polymer Bulletin*, 1980, 2, 221.

TABLE 1—THE NITROGEN AND PHOSPHORUS PERCENTAGE OF VARIOUS ORGANIC POLY(AMINIUM PHOSPHATE)S

		P% Calcd. (Found)	N% Calcd. (Found)
Poly(thioaminouronium phosphate) ($C_4H_8N_2O_2PS$) _n	Ia	18.12 (18.10)	24.56 (24.26)
Poly(1,3-dicarboxy propyl aminium phosphate) ($C_8H_{10}O_7NH$) _n	Ib	18.65 (18.70)	6.16 (6.13)
Poly(1-carboxyethyl aminium phosphate) ($C_2H_5O_2NP$) _n	Ic	18.34 (18.39)	8.28 (8.20)
Poly(<i>m</i> -hydroxyanilinium phosphate) ($C_8H_8O_4NP$) _n	Id	16.40 (16.36)	7.40 (7.36)
Poly(1,2-dicarboxyethyl aminium phosphate) ($C_4H_8O_7NP$) _n	Ie	14.55 (14.50)	6.57 (6.59)
Poly(acrylamidium phosphate) ($C_8H_8O_4NP$) _n	If	20.52 (20.48)	9.27 (9.25)
Poly(isopropyl aminium phosphate) ($C_8H_{10}O_5NP$) _n	Ig	22.27 (22.16)	10.06 (9.96)
Poly(propionamidium phosphate) ($C_8H_8O_4NP$) _n	Ih	20.23 (20.18)	9.14 (9.04)
Poly(thioacetyl aminium phosphate) ($C_8H_8O_5SNP$) _n	Ii	19.97 (19.84)	9.02 (8.96)

TABLE 2—THE R_f AND R_g VALUES OF VARIOUS POLY(AMINIUM PHOSPHATE)S

Substance	1 run (10 hr)		2 run (15 hr)	
	R_f	R_g	R_f	R_g
$NH_4H_2PO_4$	0.79	—	0.80	—
$Na_2P_2O_7$	0.39	0.49	0.41	0.51
($LiPO_3$) _n	0.02	0.02	0.04	0.05
Ia	0.07	0.09	0.14	0.18
Ib	0.07	0.09	0.13	0.16
Ic	0.06	0.07	0.11	0.14
Id	0.07	0.08	0.12	0.10
Ie	0.07	0.09	0.13	0.17
If	0.06	0.07	0.11	0.14
Ig	0.05	0.06	0.11	0.13
Ih	0.06	0.06	0.11	0.14
Ii	0.07	0.08	0.12	0.15

Paper chromatographic studies⁹: Whatman chromatographic paper (number 1) was employed for paper chromatographic studies. R_f and R_g values were measured in a New Ebel's¹⁷ solvent by an ascending technique.

Conductance studies: Conductance¹⁰ were measured at different dilutions with the help of a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a Philips conductivity cell (cell factor 1.49).

Titration of poly(phosphoric acid)s¹¹: The number average molecular weights (M_n) of poly(aminium phosphate)s were determined by end-group titration with 0.1M sodium hydroxide by using a pH meter (systronic type) having a glass and a calomel electrode. The poly(phosphoric acid) solutions used for the titration purpose were obtained by passing the aqueous solution of these poly(aminium phosphate)s through a column of cation exchange resin (Amberlite IR 45-H⁺ form)^{13,14}.

Viscosity measurements: The viscosity data were obtained by employing an Ostwald viscometer having an efflux time of 130-180 sec in a thermostatic bath (Toshniwal type), at $30 \pm 0.01^\circ$. Densities were measured with the help of a pycnometer of 11 ml capacity. All measurements were carried out after 12 hr of dissolution when the solutions attained stability.

Results and Discussion

Paper chromatograms of $(BHPO_3)_n$ derivatives were run in a New Ebel's¹⁷ solvent. This solvent was preferred over other solvents because it gives better separation and fairly large R_f values for cyclic as well as chain phosphates. Well defined spots were observed for all the polymeric derivatives (I_a-I_i). Table 2 contains R_f and R_g values for $(BHPO_3)_n$ derivatives. These values fall in the range for those of the poly(lithium phosphate) and

Graham's salt. A plot (Fig. 1) of R_f values versus negative logarithm of chain length ($-\log n_n$) gives a straight line varying with the degree of polymerization. It is indicative of the fact that the basicity and molar volumes of the organic aminium

Fig. 1. A plot of R_f values versus negative log of chain length of various poly(aminium phosphate)s.
 Ia. ○-Poly(thioaminouronium phosphate)
 Ib. △-Poly(1,3-dicarboxy propyl aminium phosphate)
 Ic. ■-Poly(1-carboxyethyl aminium phosphate)
 Id. ▲-Poly(*m*-hydroxyanilinium phosphate)
 Ie. ●-Poly(1,2-dicarboxyethyl aminium phosphate)
 If. ▽-Poly(acrylamidium phosphate)
 Ig. ●-Poly(isopropyl aminium phosphate)
 Ih. ▼-Poly(propionamidium phosphate)
 Ii. ○-Poly(thioacetyl aminium phosphate)

cations play an important role in the precipitation of fractions differing in chain length consisting of $(PO_3)_n$ units in isopropanol-water mixtures. The chromatograms also show two more spots of weak intensity in addition to that for high molecular weight polymeric phosphates. The R_f and R_g values for these spots correspond to those for trimetaphosphate and orthophosphate derivatives. It is due to the initial hydrolysis of polyphosphate chain during dissolution as reported in the case of alkali metal polyphosphates¹⁸. However, the hydrolysis

of the poly(amimum phosphate) occurs to the extent of 2-4% only during the preparation of the solution¹⁹.

Fig. 2 shows a plot of log of equivalent conductance versus negative log of concentration. It consists of straight lines which run almost parallel to each other. Many poly(electrolytes), Graham's salt and complex polymetaphosphates show similar kind of curves drawn between logarithm of equivalent conductance versus negative logarithm of concentration. This kind of behaviour can be explained on the basis of Fuoss model²⁰. Thus, conductance studies are indicative of the poly electrolytic nature of the (BHPO_s)_n derivatives.

Fig. 2. A plot of log equivalent conductance versus negative log of concentration of various poly(amimum phosphate)s.

Ia = □, Ib = ○, Ic = ▲,
 Id = ●, Ie = ■, If = ⊙,
 Ig = ▼, Ih = ▽, Ii = △,

The viscosity of (BHPO_s)_n derivatives in 0.035N and 0.07N sodium chloride solution²¹ confirms the long chain polymeric character of these derivatives. The reduced (η_{sp}/C) and inherent viscosities ($\ln \eta_r/C$) were plotted against concentration (Fig. 3). Straight lines are obtained which on extrapolation intersect at the same point on Y-axis. This kind of behaviour is characteristic of linear polymers²². The values for Huggins constant k' and k'' were also calculated.

The values for the sum of $k'+k''$ (Table 4) corresponds to 0.5 to 0.6 which are again characteristic of linear chain polymers. The viscosity average molecular weights were determined by using the equation proposed by Strauss²³.

Fig. 3. A plot of reduced viscosity and inherent viscosity versus concentration of various poly(amimum phosphate)s.

Ia = ■, Ib = ▼, Ic = ●,
 Id = □, Ie = ■, If = ▲,
 Ig = ○, Ih = △, Ii = □,

Mehrotra and Gupta²⁴ have calculated the viscosity average molecular weights of Graham's salt in 0.035N sodium chloride solution instead of sodium bromide and observed that the nature of the swamping electrolyte did not change the reduced viscosity appreciably. The value of K was checked by Gupta²⁴ in 0.035N sodium chloride solution and it was found to correspond to the same value within experimental errors as given by Strauss *et al*²⁵. Hence, the viscosity measurements of poly(amimum phosphate) solutions were carried out in 0.035N sodium chloride solution and viscosity average (M_w) weights were calculated by using the value of K equal to 1.76×10^{-5} and a unit value for that of constant 'a'. The M_w values so obtained are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3—THE VALUES OF M_n , η , M_w , $[G_n]$ AND M_w VALUES FOR VARIOUS POLY(AMIMUM PHOSPHATE)S

Substance	M_n	η	M_w	$[G_n]$	M_w
Ia	2590	0.0995	5655	0.0997	5664
Ib	2760	0.1140	6477	0.1200	6812
Ic	3300	0.1230	6988	0.1250	7102
Id	2315	0.1200	6818	0.1220	6931
Ie	2600	0.0980	5568	0.0990	5667
If	3444	0.1275	7244	0.1300	7389
Ig	3605	0.1495	8495	0.1500	8522
Ih	3592	0.1395	7926	0.1400	7954
Ii	2960	0.1225	6960	0.1250	7102

Nagy *et al*²⁵ have suggested an improved graphical method for the determination of M_w values for the chain polymers by calculating the intrinsic

viscosity from the viscometric data. The usual straight line relationship between reduced viscosity and concentration is expressed as :

$$Y = ax + b \quad \dots (1)$$

where $Y = \eta_{sp}/C$; $x = \text{concentration}$; 'a' and 'b' are slope and intercept respectively.

Equation (1) is replaced with the linear transformation

$$G = AF + B \quad \dots (2)$$

where the variables G and F are denoted as :

$$G = Y/\alpha - x \text{ and } F = \frac{x}{\alpha - x} \quad \dots (3)$$

and the parameters are $a = A - B$ and $b' = B - \alpha$.. (4)

In the above equation $Y = \eta_{sp}/C$ and α is the sum of x_m and x_M i.e., the sum of the minimum and maximum independent variable i.e., concentration and A (slope) and B (intercept) are the characteristic constants.

Fig. 4 shows a plot of variable G versus F. The extrapolation of this graph to zero concentration gives the values of parameter B. The values of improved intrinsic viscosity were then calculated from equation (4) with the help of parameter B. The value of α , in equation (4) equal to one has been

Fig. 4. A plot of variable G versus F of various poly(aminium-phosphate)s.

- | | | |
|-----------------------|---------------------|------------------|
| Ia = $\blacktriangle$ | Ib = ∇ | Ic = $\triangle$ |
| Id = $\square$ | Ie = $\blacksquare$ | If = $\circ$ |
| Ig = $\circ$ | Ih = $\square$ | Ii = ∇ |
- (same as Ic)

used for these polymer derivatives. So, the value of B directly represents the improved value intrinsic

viscosity. But in order to avoid confusion in these two values of intrinsic viscosity, the one obtained by usual plot of η_{sp}/C vs C (Fig. 3) is represented by $[\eta]$ and the one obtained by equation (4) is represented by $[G_n]$. Both these values are recorded in Table 3. It is revealed from the table that both these values differ by 2-4%. However, the suggested method ensures an uniform error distribution in the measurement of viscosity data which deviates from the straight line relationship in usual graphical method of η_{sp}/C vs C at higher dilutions. Hence, the improved values of intrinsic viscosity $[G_n]$ can be used for calculating the more reliable viscosity average molecular weights according to the equation (5).

$$(x_M + x_m)[G_n]_{c \rightarrow 0} = 1.76 \times 10^{-5} M_w^* \quad (5)$$

The M_w^* values so obtained are recorded in Table 3.

The viscosity of $(\text{BHPO}_3)_n$ derivatives were also determined in 0.07N sodium chloride solution²¹. The values for intrinsic viscosity in 0.07N and 0.035N sodium chloride solution are recorded in Table 4. From the table it is observed that the

TABLE 4—INTRINSIC VISCOSITY VALUES IN 0.035N AND 0.07N SODIUM CHLORIDE AND av. $k' + k''$ FOR POLY(AMINIUM PHOSPHATE)s

	$[\eta]$ in 0.035N NaCl	$[\eta]$ in 0.07N NaCl	av. $k' + k''$
Ia	0.0995	—	0.65
Ib	0.1140	0.0095	0.56
Ic	0.1230	—	0.62
Id	0.1200	0.1080	0.57
Ie	0.0980	—	0.61
If	0.1275	0.1100	0.55
Ig	0.1495	0.1380	0.51
Ih	0.1395	0.1275	0.53
Ii	0.1225	—	0.54

intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ is decreased in 0.07N sodium chloride which suggests that increase in concentration of swamping electrolyte affects the draining behaviour of these polymers.

The number average molecular weights (M_n) determined from end-group titration were found to be in the range 3000-4000. The ratio of M_w/M_n corresponds to about 2.1 to 2.3 which is indicative of most probable distribution of molecular weight in the case of these poly(aminium phosphate)s. Van-Wazer²⁶ has suggested a Poisson distribution in case of middle group of the $(\text{PO}_3)_n$ chain in case of alkali metal phosphates i.e., the viscosity average molecular weight is nearly equal to the number average molecular weight.

The conclusion rests on an approach used by Flory²⁷ in considering the random reorganization in linear organic polymers. It was assumed that terminal phosphate groups of the P-O-P chain are not involved in the reorganization process. Ohashi

et al²¹ determined the viscosities of sodium phosphates and Graham's salt. It has been stated that distribution of molecular weights is not exactly the Poisson distribution for lower molecular weight (lower than 10300) samples. In general for a poly-disperse polymer

$$M_w > M_v > M_n$$

with differences increasing as the molecular weight distribution broadens. The ratio M_w/M_n can be taken as a measure of distribution of molecular weight in a polymer sample. This ratio is approximately two for polymers having a 'most probable distribution' as expected in case of step reaction (condensation) polymerization²². As poly(aminium phosphate)s have been isolated by reacting poly(lithium phosphate)s having weight average molecular weights in the range 8000-10000, the ratio of M_w/M_n for these polymers is more than two also. Therefore, it can be predicted that molecular weight distribution for poly(aminium phosphate) is not exactly Poisson and corresponds to a 'most probable distribution' as expected in case of linear chain polymers.

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